

MODERN SPORT: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

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Abstract: *Modern sport is a powerful industry that includes a special system for the production of sports records. It involves along with athletes and coaches, managers, sports doctors, psychologists, researchers. The media are constantly promoting large-scale competition to the level of the main events of the life of society. However, one should not represent modern sport as a single phenomenon with one goal, function and general patterns of development. Modern sports are many-sided and varied. The system of sports includes such varieties as mass, children and youth, school, student sports, which solve the problems of health improvement and the formation of sports culture of the younger generation. Sports of the highest achievements (Olympic and professional sports) is aimed at achieving high sports results and victories. These varieties share common functions: entertainment, political, economic. The sport of excellence broadcasts a special example of a lifestyle, a way success, demonstrates high sports technique, the ability to beat rival. For many viewers, this model becomes a model for imitation not only in sports, but also in other spheres of life. However, elite sport has generated a large number of contradictions that do not allow modern sport to develop positively, often discredit it and form a negative attitude of people, especially parents, to sports. Increasingly, public opinion evaluates modern sport as a dangerous sphere for human's activities. Purpose of the study: to conduct a sociological analysis of the contradictions of modern sports and propose ways to overcome them.*

Keywords— modern sports, elite sports, Olympic and professional sports.

1. INTRODUCTION

Among the most acute contradictions in the development of sports in modern society is the myth that sport is perhaps the only and main factor in maintaining and strengthening health. No one disputes the preventive value of exercise. However, you need to understand that this is just one of the factors that make up a healthy lifestyle. In addition to sports, human health is influenced by the environmental situation, the regime and quality of nutrition, the presence of bad habits, the standard of living, heredity, etc. Therefore, one should not directly link the state of health and sports. In addition, there are known tragic cases that happened to outstanding young athletes due to injuries and high sports loads. It is enough to give an example of the tragic fate of Alexei Cherepanov, when the heart of a young and promising athlete. Has already become familiar a picture when athletes, skiers, biathletes after passing the distance "dead" fall on the track of the stadium or on the track [1].

2. MAIN PART

Sports of the highest achievements is associated with the risk and the need to influence the maximum permissible physical activity on the body. Unfortunately, due to a number of circumstances (disposition to win at any cost, doping), an athlete goes over the edge of what is permissible and damages his own health, and sometimes the health of an opponent.

Currently, the number of new sports, especially extreme ones, is rapidly increasing: mountain biking, quads, freestyle, scooters and much more. Extreme sports sometimes supplant classical ones - skiing, athletics, gymnastics. However, a person cannot be prohibited from engaging in any kind of sport and learning the capabilities of his own body. Moreover, often in life we are faced with situations when only a complete concentration of forces allows us avoid danger. And the more physical strength a person has, the less health losses he gets out of a difficult situation. Sport helps to simulate problem situations and find ways out of them. Therefore, each person must decide to what level of sports to strive for achievements.

The contradiction associated with sports and the health of an athlete can be resolved by improving sports equipment, competition rules, improving the material and technical equipment of sports bases, prevention health, medical control over the health of athletes, as well as improving the quality of professional training of the coaching staff. However, the problem of "sport and health" remains unresolved so far.

The next contradiction in the field of elite sports is that many sports have become rapidly "younger". Record results are achieved by adolescents, almost children, for example, in sports such as rhythmic and artistic gymnastics, figure

skating. In other sports, the age of the winners also has a noticeable tendency to decrease (O. Korbut, M. Filatova, L. Mukhina, T. Lepinski, Yu. Lipnitskaya achieved the highest results at the age of 14). It is clear that young athletes can also win the highest ranked competitions. However, the essence of

the problem is that there is a forced training of a young athlete without taking into account

age indicators of its development.

Compounding this problem is the presence of a system selection of talented children when not

sports for the child, and the child for sports. Selection is a serious psychological stress for many children and parents, which often pushes the child away from sports forever. The use of special technologies, "worked out" on the adult contingent, without adaptation

leads them to the methodology of youth sports to premature "pumping" of a young athlete, and sports longevity is out of the question.

This is a contradiction in the field of youth

sport ultimately distorts the essence of sport, cripple's athletes physically and mentally.

Another contradiction, seriously undermining the foundations of sports, is generated by the system of contractual victories that are organized in hotel numbers of judges, in the offices of managers, that is, far from gyms, playgrounds, fields. The displacement of the competitive factor has become significant, especially in team sports. According to researchers, a considerable number of football and hockey championship matches are sold out in advance. This, of course, affects the moral foundations of athletes, as well as the entertainment of sports. Therefore, we often see half-empty stands and disappointed fans.

In professional sports, as well as in show business, big money "spins". But the fight for the "purity" of sports, of course, must be waged. An equally difficult situation is developing in the pharmacological service of sports. Using doping, which began in the 1970s and 1980s, has spread to all sports. Problem doping is perceived ambiguously in society.

Of course, in this way sport wins in entertainment, but it loses much more in humanity. Indeed, subject to the use of doping, we are not talking about identifying the strongest, in this case there is a struggle between doctors and pharmacologists who can most successfully "pump up" athlete. Currently allow this the problem is hardly possible, since in modern sports, the tendencies to conquer victory at any cost only intensify and develop.

Doping is not a private practice in sports doctors, and a well-thought-out system of scientific, methodological and medical support. At the same time, there is no doubt that that a modern athlete experiences colossal training loads and his body unable to recover quickly without help pharmacological agents. If not use maintenance drugs, the athlete will not able to train in modern volumes and preset modes of intensity, and negative the consequences of stress will lead to pathological changes in his body and psyche. Therefore, sports doctors demand to legitimize some pharmacological agents that will help athletes to cope with excessive stress and stress, increase

resistance the body for colds, will increase pain threshold in the treatment of sports injuries.

Nobody forbids people of extreme professions (miners, oilmen, astronauts) to restore their working capacity with the help of pharmacological means. Then why can't a professional athlete be helped to reduce recovery time from injury or excessive training stress?

The activities of specially created anti-doping organizations did not meet expectations: doping scandals do not subside in the society.

Athletes convicted of doping are closed for a long time the road to big sport, there are deprived of sports awards, they become in a row people who are rejected by society.

3. CONCLUSION

Thus, the way to solve these and others social contradictions of modern sports in strengthening the educational, scientific and cultural components of sports activities. Formation and intensive development of sports cultures can significantly increase the potential modern sports and form a positive public opinion to seek new resources for mass engagement into the sports movement.

4. REFERENCES

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